

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D7.1 - Communication and Dissemination Plan

Authors:

LIMA (Claudia BRIONGOS, Segis VERDAGUER)

January 2024 (M29) - WP7, D7.1

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101032450. The views expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author/s and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Technical References

Project Acronym	ePLANET
Project Title	European Public Authorities' Network for driving the Energy Transition

Deliverable No.	D7.1
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP7 - Communication and Dissemination
Lead beneficiary	9 - LIMA
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	1 - CIMNE
Due date of deliverable	31/12/2023
Actual submission date	05/01/2024

Authors	Segis Verdaguer - LIMA, Claudia Briongos - LIMA, Olga Barrachina - LIMA
Contributors	Josep Mayos - CIMNE, Gerard Laguna - CIMNE

Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
0.1	21/11/21	First version M3, circulated for revision	CB and SV (LIMA)
0.2	22/11/21	Revision	JM (CIMNE)
1.0	24/11/21	Second version M3, circulated for revision	SV (LIMA)
1.1	26/11/21	Format changes	SV (LIMA), JM (CIMNE)
2.0	04/09/22	First version of M15 update	CB and SV (LIMA)
2.1	07/11/22	2 nd version of M15, circulated for revision	CB and SV (LIMA)
2.2	15/11/22	Revision	ES (3OC)
3.0	15/10/23	First version of M28 update	OB (LIMA)
3.1	04/01/24	2 nd version of M28 update	SV (LIMA)

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Executive Summary

This document is the third (and last) release of ePLANET's Communication and Dissemination plan, which updates the communication strategy already fixed in the first version of the document, and the corresponding activities.

It is developed to spread the knowledge generated during ePLANET project, a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CA	Consortium Agreement
CMP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
ESCO	Energy Services Companies
ET	Energy Transition
ETM	Energy Transition Measures
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
MoA	Memorandum of Adhesion
PA	Public Authority
PP	Project partner
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
TG	Target Groups
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

The Communication and Dissemination Plan is part of the activities of Work Package 7, which centralizes most of the coordination and implementation of project's communication and dissemination activities. Work Package 7 consists of different tasks:

- T7.1: Communication and Dissemination plan and coordination
- T7.2: Visual identity
- T7.3: Project website
- T7.4: Promotional material
- T7.5: Conferences
- T7.6: Social media
- T7.7: Newsletters and press releases
- T7.8: Final event

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will constitute the core document outlining the activities at the basis of the project's dissemination and communication activities, and will set up and manage an effective communication and dissemination strategy to guarantee the scientific, professional and public coverage of the project results.

It will be subject to revision every 12 months in order to fine tune the dissemination and communication objectives with project results, and include potential new communication tools and targets that may appear over time. Thus, this 3rd Communication and Dissemination Plan will aim at selecting which results should be given priority and how they need to be communicated within the final year of the project.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

2.1 Overall objectives

All the communication and dissemination activities have been designed in order to have an impact on the specific segmented target audiences of the project. Main objectives of communication and dissemination activities are:

- Guaranteeing the scientific and public coverage of the project results.
- Supporting optimal conditions and solutions for the replication and exploitation of the project outcomes.
- Consolidating the project visibility among public authorities and stakeholders at EU level to enhance awareness.

These objectives are closely related with European “Communication EU research and innovation guidance for project participants” handbook, which highlights the need to communicate the benefits of EU funded projects to the whole society.

2.2 Communication and dissemination principles

The communication activities will be grouped in and planned at four levels, according to their communication objectives:

Pilot territories level

Communication and marketing to ensure the deployment of the ePLANET project within pilot regions. Stakeholder engagement and local authorities awareness raising. The communication will consist in communicating information about the specific pilot case, its milestones, progresses, capacity building activities and news. The project website, social media and local press will be the key communication channels. Local language will be prioritized.

Supra-regional and national level

Communication and marketing to ensure the scale-up of ePLANET pilots to the whole region/state, depending on the pilot case, and inform stakeholders, public authorities (local, regional and national) and general public. The communication will be focused on explaining the project and its potential scale-up to neighbour regions around pilot cases, including progresses and news. The project website and social media will be the key communication channels. Local language and English will be used.

Replication at wide EU level

Broader communication, to all EU stakeholders to maximize the replication and exploitation of ePLANET networks and governance at EU level. This communication will

be focused on explaining the project and its contributions to ET to other EU regions, who seeing the achievements of the pilot territories, will see an opportunity for their region by participating in the replication phase and implement the project results. The website and social media will be the key communication channels. English language will be prioritized.

Mainstream level

Communicate project objectives, progresses and results EU wide to broader audience and different target groups. This communication level includes all general communication activities and channels.

Figure 2-1 - Principle schema of communication and dissemination activities

2.3 Three-tier approach

The three-tier approach follows a methodology used to increase the efficiency of engagement strategies in collaborative scenarios. The level of engagement and involvement of people and entities on a specific subject or activity depends largely on their own motivations. Dividing a group into different subgroups -depending on their degree of motivation will allow the rationalisation of resources and the deployment of tailor-made activities depending on the target degree of motivation: most engaged tier will be involved in more requesting activities, and less engaged tier will have lighter involvement in activities.

Figure 2-2 - Three-tier approach principle

The three-tier approach will be applied in the different ePLANET engagement activities, by creating 3 different groups with progressive engagement levels. First tier for the less motivated. Third tier for the most motivated. Public authorities and stakeholders will have the possibility to participate in any of the groups, depending on their own motivations and the responsibilities they can assume. This engagement approach will maximise the further adoption of ePLANET tools by public authorities.

The 3rd level of engagement of the three-tier approach in ePLANET project will be mainly reserved to the stakeholders and public authorities participating in the ePLANET Stakeholder Forum. The members will be the first adopters of ePLANET tools and methodologies. On the other hand, 1st and 2nd levels of engagement will be open to the whole public sector for both the scale-up of ePLANET outcomes within the pilot regions and the national and EU-wide replication, working with the objective to shift them on to upper level of engagement.

Table 2-1: Activities and responsibilities following the three-tier approach

		LEVEL 1	LEVEL 2	LEVEL 3
ACTIVITIES	Newsletter	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Public webinars	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Private webinars	--	Yes	Yes
	Workshops	--	Yes	Yes
	Site-visits	--	Yes	Yes
	Stakeholders Forum	--	--	Yes
RESPONSIBILITIES	Memorandum of Adhesion	--	Yes	Yes
	Use and feedback of ePLANET platform	--	Yes	Yes
	Designation of ePLANET facilitator	--	Yes	Yes
	Participation in working groups	--	--	Yes
	Participation in Stakeholders Forum's meetings	--	--	Yes

3 Target audience and stakeholders maps

3.1 Internal target audience

Internal communication, among ePLANET project partners, needs to be fluid and frequent: it is important not only to achieve good results, but also to deliver good external communication.

Regular face to face and online meetings will facilitate direct interaction, while e-mails are more suitable to exchange about more concise aspects (project advancement, encountered difficulties, deliverables, results and other material to communicate, etc.).

Project coordinator is in charge to ensure the smooth communication at internal level.

3.2 External target audience

The external target audience is composed of 4 main groups, which have been defined as follow:

- TG1: local, regional and national authorities, initiatives for PA
- TG2: sustainability experts, urban planners, ESCOs & investors in sustainability
- TG3: scientific community and related EU projects
- TG4: general public

These target audiences will also be classified into 3 different groups depending on the level of motivation and implication in the project, following the “three-tier approach”.

Different actions will be also carried out depending on the geographical location of the target audiences (Greece, Catalonia or Czech Republic). Besides, the communication activities will be personalised based on the situation of the public, whether they are in the pilot site, the replication level or the mainstream level.

3.3 Stakeholders maps

Given the target audience of the ePLANET project, an initial survey has been conducted within the consortium, to potentially identify a first set of stakeholders that could be engaged within the project development. As shown in next figures, the relevance of the different target audience and potential key stakeholders will vary from one pilot-site to another. Following protection data regulations, the different data has been anonymized.

- Legend**
- Local authorities
 - Regional authorities
 - Sustainability experts
 - EU initiatives
 - Universities
 - Investors
 - Initiatives PA
 - EU Projects
 - Research Centres
 - Public institutes
 - National authorities

Figure 3-1 - Stakeholder map

3.4 Specific target audience message

3.4.1 TG1: Local, regional and national authorities, initiatives for PA

OBJECTIVE	<p>Authorities in all kind of levels are an important target audience, as they are the ones who will use the ePLANET platform and will be active members of the clustering governance strategy. The specific objective for this group is to show them the positive impact of this platform and to create awareness of the need to change the current ET governance and unify the different processes, as this will lead to an improvement of the vertical and horizontal governance of ET</p>
MESSAGE	<p>ePLANET is designed for the whole community of EU public authorities. It will foster the engagement of public authorities into ePLANET activities, sharing their ET data and fostering the identification of potential synergies and common benefits from the other initiatives and public authorities, in a non-time-consuming. It is important to remark this fact, that the time they will spend learning how to use the platform is a well invested time, as they will get more positive impact and they will save time in long-term.</p> <p>ePLANET will improve the vertical and horizontal governance of ET at the whole territory, improving the accomplishment of the national energy savings and RES objectives. It will help ministries to foster collaboration and horizontal governance, increasing the adoption of coordinated strategies at energy, mobility, financing and regulatory level, amongst others. Adhesion to MoA for long-term commitment in ET. Thus, the adoption of ETM within their whole territory will be accelerated thanks to ePLANET outcomes</p>

3.4.2 TG2: Sustainability experts, urban planners, ESCO's and investors

OBJECTIVE	<p>This target group includes any expert supporting public authorities on the definition and deployment of SECAPs, ET plans and ETM, including consultancies, engineering, sustainability experts, urban planners, ESCOs and investors in sustainability. While they will not be directly using the ePLANET platform or members of the clustering governance, it is considered a critical stakeholder group to achieve project results. The specific objective for this group is to show them the benefits of the new clustering governance and the use of the ePLANET platform</p>
MESSAGE	<p>Awareness of the potential of ePLANET outcomes to become a decision-making supporting tool for public authorities. They need to help -as experts, engineering, consultancy, etc- public authorities on the identification of most appropriate ET strategies. Knowledge sharing is essential to accelerate the uptake of ET measures at local level.</p>

3.4.3 TG3: Scientific community and related EU projects

OBJECTIVE	The specific objectives regarding the scientific community are creating awareness of the potential of ePLANET outcomes to become a decision-making supporting tool for public authorities. Besides, it is also important to establish synergies with the scientific community in order to open opportunities for future collaboration and to spread and share technical knowledge.
MESSAGE	<p>ePLANET is conceived as a methodology for Multi-Level Governance of ET supported by a Digital Platform tool, to increase the efficiency of the ET decision making process in public authorities. It will allow cities and municipalities to introduce their plans in a digital form that can be shared, compared, monitored and aggregated with other related local or regional public authorities' plans across the territory. It will enable visibility, synchronization, discussion and coherence of plans and actions of the different public authorities in specific territories or geographical scopes, enhancing already established relations between them, and highlighting all the benefits of coordinated actions and collaborative planning.</p> <p>ePLANET will foster the digital transformation of sustainable energy plans by promoting the first platform to combine a global set of harmonized measures and policies within a big-data analytics engine, allowing systematic data integration in digital computer processing enabled form, direct comparison and analysis of ET measures, policies and data through a Common Data Model.</p>

3.4.4 TG4: General Public

OBJECTIVE	The main objective for the general public is to raise awareness on ET strategies and measures, and ePLANET project & outcomes.
MESSAGE	It is important that the general public realises about the steps governments are taking in the energetic transition and the eco-friendly scope. ePLANET is a platform which is allowing this transformation to happen by fostering sustainable energy plans and creating a hegemonic language between the different governments, not only horizontally, but also vertically.

4 Communication and dissemination channels

4.1 Website

As a key channel for interaction with the engaged stakeholders of the project and the selected target groups, a project website will be created. However, it will not be the only tool used to disseminate information about the progress and the results achieved by the project, it will be also a communication tool to the general public. In addition to the official project website, it will contain a link to the digital ePLANET platform. It will be a repository of information, considered as a lively tool with continuously updated contents (news and press releases, original articles and interviews, posts of project-related news from external sources, cross-linking).

The website will be available in English, with options to change most of the content to the languages of the pilot territories, developed by the partners themselves. In addition, each project partner will create a special section on its own website in its national language, describing briefly the project and dedicated to the promotion of its results.

Beginning 2024, the project website will get an important update, to highlight the most relevant project outcomes. In particular, a new section will be created in relation to the guidelines and best practices in Energy Transition, developed in WP6. This will be a completely new section allowing for an easy identification and selection of best practices on different thematic areas (governance, digitalisation, etc), following the outcomes of the deliverable D6.5. Furthermore, the resource section will also be modified to highlight the most relevant deliverables for external public. All the changes will be performed before end of February'24.

4.2 Social networks

Social media represents another essential channel for mainstream communication as well as specific target audience. Specific ePLANET profiles have been developed.

LIMA Association is the main responsible for managing the project's social media accounts but all ePLANET partners are encouraged to widen the coverage of the project through their own social media channels. Their support is of high importance to inform LIMA about events and developments on one hand, and to increase the audience by promoting and participating in the different social networks on the other hand.

We have created a social media communication plan which consists mainly in:

- Scheduling to publish at least twice a week.
- Writing in a more personal way and using impacting messages to get closer to the general public.
- Using interesting and good quality pictures to be able to use the same content at the different channels.
- Planning the communication content one month in advance, so providing a communication calendar.

2024 activity in social networks within 2024 will be focused on the capacity building actions as well as on the dissemination of project videos as well as key results of the project (e.g. repository of best practices, governance strategy, etc).

4.2.1 LinkedIn

As LinkedIn is a professional network, it will be used to send messages to TG2 and TG3, but also to TG1. We will publish regularly sharing short information about the project, but once a month a longer article with more explanations will be published.

4.2.2 Twitter

Twitter is the most used platform among our target groups, therefore it is an important tool for the communication and dissemination plan. It will be very useful to create connections with other EU projects and also to reach the general public.

4.2.3 YouTube

YouTube is a very important tool which will not be used as the other social networks because there will not be regular publications. It will work as a repository of videos, including webinars and workshops, so that everybody have access to them if they missed the date where the webinar or workshop took place.

A total of 20 videos will be uploaded by the end of the project.

4.3 Press-releases & e-Newsletter

Good press coverage is also essential to increase the long-term visibility of the project, and so the impact of the project. In the course of the project, 16 press releases will be produced and distributed, most of them written in the pilot region languages and distributed on local press. Nevertheless, some press releases will be written in English and distributed to a broader EU audience.

A digital Newsletter to share projects updates and news will be created. It will be written in English, and distributed to web registered users and will be made publicly available on the project website, every 6 months.

4.4 Webinars & workshops

As far as webinars & workshops are concerned, there will be a total number of 33, 24 focused on the pilot regions, and 9 focused on the replication and networking across EU.

In order to achieve the objectives of the WP 4, to clarify how to better deploy ET measures and actions, there will be 2 public webinars and 4 private webinars per pilot, depending on the target audiences (3-tier approach). Besides, a series of 6 private thematic workshops (2 per pilot) will be organised to bring in knowledge and hands-on material to the pilot regions. The workshops will consist on keynotes and roundtables with experts on the prioritised topics.

In the process of replication and networking there will be a total of 6 scale-up webinars (2 per pilot) and 3 workshops in order to push public stakeholders from Level 1 to Level 2 (or even 3) of the three-tier approach.

While the agenda of each webinar will be defined within their organization, it is already possible to identify some must topics:

- Peer mentoring, where the municipalities already familiar with the platform, thanks to the pilots, demonstrate its utility to new users.
- Showcase of platform's features.

The webinars will be recorded and made available online both on the ePLANET website and on the project partners' ones, so to allow municipalities which could not attend the webinars to still have the possibility to be engaged.

At the end of each webinar, PPs will draft a summary report.

4.5 Communication videos

Communication videos will be a key way to raise awareness on the opportunities of using ePLANET platform and governance strategies, and so attract public authorities on the adoption of ePLANET outcomes.

Several videos will be created, in close cooperation with WP2, WP4 and pilot partners:

- 1 short constitutional video (2-minutes length) to explain the project approach and first achievements. This video has already been created and uploaded to the ePLANET Youtube channel.
- 3 regional videos (2-minutes length) for project scale up. One per pilot territory (regional language). The video structure is not still defined, but probably it will include common content with some specific parts for each pilot territory.
- 2 EU wide videos (2 minutes length) for replication.

4.6 Project leaflets & brochures

The promotional material will consist of:

- A project leaflet with objectives, expected results and methodology, printed in 4 languages. The project leaflet has already been created. It's available within the ePLANET website.
- A project brochure in English highlighting the project approach and first achievements.

4.7 Conferences and scientific publications

PPs will present ePLANET platform and governance methodology into at least 8 conferences to enlarge the dissemination reach. In particular: 2 conferences per pilot country + 2 in other EU regions. Scientific papers will be produced to disseminate the project's proceedings and results (CRES and CIMNE).

4.8 Visual identity handbook

To support the project's communication and dissemination mission, an initial set of communication materials will be produced, including project identity, templates for deliverables and templates for presentations.

5 Monitoring

5.1 What to monitor

It's important to know the audience that has been reached by the project, both in quantitative and qualitative parameters. The reactions caused by the project and the level of satisfaction of the audience are important to better focus the following communication actions.

Monitoring activities will follow next scheme:

Figure 5-1 - Principles of monitoring and evaluation

5.2 Communication and dissemination KPIs

Next tables include the means of evaluation of the different communication and dissemination activities. The related KPIs are the objectives at the end of the project. The progress of the different KPIs at M24 is also included. For the regional scaling up videos, we consider 0 views as they have been uploaded to Youtube channel at M24, so with no time to consider the views.

Table 5-1: Communication activities KPIs

COMMUNICATION AREA	KPIs	M36	M12	M24
PROJECT WEBSITE	Number of unique visitors (Google Analytics)	4.000	719	2.866
	Number of visits (monthly average) (Google Analytics)	100	82	336
TWITTER	Number of followers	500	194	387
	Number of impressions	+10.000	8.358	+21.000
LINKEDIN	Number of members	500	126	262
	Number of shares	+300	25	155
YOUTUBE	Institutional video - number of visualisations	1.000	103	982
	Regional videos (explaining project) - total visualisations	1.500	--	--
	EU-wide videos - number of total visualisations	1.000	--	--

NEWSLETTER	Number of publications	6	1	4
PRESS RELEASES	Number of press-releases	16	1	7

Table 5-2: Dissemination activities KPIs

DISSEMINATION AREA	KPIs	M36	M24
STAKEHOLDERS FORUM	Engaged stakeholders	150	120
WEBINARS & WORKSHOPS	Number of attendees (total) in:		
	User empowerment private webinars	960	83
	User empowerment public webinars	720	--
	User empowerment private workshops	240	68
	Scaling-up webinars	720	--
	Scaling-up workshops	120	--
CONFERENCES & EVENTS	Number of attendees (total) in:		
	Presentation to conferences	320	160
	Final event	50	--
SITE VISITS	Number of attendees (total)	75	--

6 Dissemination of results & open access

6.1 Obligation to disseminate results

Dissemination (Grant Agreement - article 29) is a separate obligation (e.g. through scientific articles and conferences). In that sense, each beneficiary must “disseminate” its results as soon as possible by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means, unless it goes against their legitimate interests. This does not change the obligation to protect results, confidentiality obligations, security obligations, or the obligation to protect personal data.

6.2 Information on EU funding - Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Any communication activity related to the action and any infrastructure, equipment and major result funded by the grant (unless the Agency request to do so) must include:

- a) The EU emblem. High resolution emblems can be found here: https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/symbols/european-flag_en
- b) The following text:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101032450.

6.3 Disclaimer excluding Agency responsibility

Any disclaimer of results must indicate that these only reflect the author’s view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Example:

The views expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author/s and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

7 Specific communication actions during 3rd year

Table 7-1: Communication actions from M24 to M36

ACTION	DEADLINE
Communication and Dissemination Plan	M28
2 replicability videos (English)	M28
2 newsletter	M14, M20
8 press releases	M29, M30, M31, M32, M33, M34, M35, M36
Update of the ePLANET website (new Best Practices section, update of Resource section)	M30

8 Annex I - Communication & Dissemination activities performed

This section shows a summary of main achievements regarding Communication and Dissemination plan.

M24 - Scaling up videos (D7.8)

The project has developed 3 additional videos during the 2nd year. These 3 scaling up videos were submitted at M24, and tailored to the pilot regions, with national language and specific testimonials from the pilot region.

Figure 8-1 - Scaling up videos screenshots

M24 - Project brochure (D7.5)

A project brochure has been designed to be used as one of the key promotional materials, including the outputs of ePLANET project. The 16-pages document, in English, allows for a proper explanation of the most relevant outputs of the project. The proposed design tries to maximise the understanding of the content, using a combination of images, schemes and text. The project brochure has been submitted by M24, without any delay compared to the expected planning.

Figure 8-2 - Project brochure: example of double page section

networks, contact form, subscription to newsletter, news, languages) that are present in different sections.

Figure 8-4 - "Home" section (partial view)

Figure 8-5 - “News” section (partial view)

M9 - 1st newsletter released (T7.7)

The first ePLANET newsletter have been released by beginning June 2022, with a summary of the most relevant news of the project. The current number of subscriptions to the newsletter being small, the newsletter has also been directly distributed to the project partners (to include it on their own newsletters) as well as through LinkedIn, Twitter and the project website.

M10 - Constitutional video (D7.7)

The ePLANET constitutional video has been produced following the planned timeline.

The 2-minutes length video, available at the [ePLANET Youtube channel](#), focuses on the project goals and future outcomes to increase the interest of potential target audience into the project activities.

Figure 8-6 - Frame of the constitutional video

This constitutional video is also published through Social Media channels, like LinkedIn and Twitter, to maximise its visibility.

M9-M11 - Launch of the Open Call for Follower Regions (WP5)

The ePLANET actions include the identification and selection of different follower regions that will benefit from the project outcomes. The whole activity is included in Work Package 5, but the selection procedure has been accompanied by a communication action through the main social channels of the project, together with the creation of a specific page in the ePLANET website.

Figure 8-7 - Open Call section in the ePLANET website

M2-M14 - Social Media: LinkedIn & Twitter

The ePLANET actions include the creation of a LinkedIn “project page” and a Twitter account, which centralise all the social media communication activities. More than 320 followers have been activated, considering both platforms, during the 1st year of the project. Within this period, the communication activities have been mainly focused on information about the project objectives, the open call for follower regions and general awareness raising on the need to enhance the energy transition governance.

Figure 8-8 - LinkedIn posts

Figure 8-9 - Twitter posts

